

Rural Renaissance: Stitching Sustainability with the Amalgamation of Technology in Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab

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ABSTRACT

A tale of rural renaissance begins to play in the land of Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab. With the threads of sustainability, this paper aims to stitch together the past and future with finesse. The vision of Mehar Baba Charitable Trust (MBCT)⁶ through the integration of technology nurtures Phulkari's cultural seed. A project⁷ was initiated to bridge the gaps, unite communities and raise awareness to ensure that phulkari stands tall and proud rooted in the traditional roots of Punjab by MBCT funded by Canada Fund for Local Initiatives (CFLI)⁸. This study sheds light on the potential of technology to bridge the urban-rural divide and create a more inclusive and sustainable future for rural communities.

The study is built upon primary and secondary sources of data collection. The transformative power of technology in fostering a rural renaissance in Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab is explored, through the present study. By combining traditional craftsmanship, such as Phulkari, with digital marketing skills, the aim is to empower rural women and promote sustainable livelihoods. Through the lens of community engagement and technological innovation, the challenges faced, the strategies employed, and the positive impact observed were comprehended. The findings from this research would help in maintaining sustainability for future generations in the field of handwork with the amalgamation of digital technology. The discoveries from this investigation will guide the future expansion and duplication of the project in other areas.

Keywords: Renaissance, Phulkari, Digital Technology, Rural Women, Punjab

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INTRODUCTION

The art of embroidery has been a significant part of the history of India. Handicrafts nurtured during leisure time in every nook and corner of India showcase the artistic expression and exquisite craftsmanship of our ancestors. The traditional crafts have been passed on from generation to generation, with each area developing its unique style and pattern of embroidery. It is not only a traditional skill but also weaves the socio-economic fabric of rural people. It reflects diverse cultural heritage and a connection to our roots. Each stitch describes the story of men and women embellishing the fabric. Meticulous embroidery by rural people continues to capture and captivate the minds and hearts of the urban sector, making it the largest consumer of handicrafts produced by the former. The dynamics in urban and rural India play a crucial role in shaping India's economy. Still, greater dynamics lie inside the rural areas. On one side of the coin, rural areas constitute the vulnerable section who are deprived of basic necessities, on the other, its renaissance is an inspiring phenomenon that showcases the unlimited potential that its people hold. The Punjab region is one of its kind; the place where issues of the caste system and orthodox thinking are still prevalent, handicrafts are a significant part of each household highlighting the resilience of rural communities. GI⁹ tag has been granted to this timeless art of 'Phulkari'. Women, in particular, are crafting changes and improving livelihoods by passing the formidable crafts of India to the next generations.

Embroidery is a symbol of empowerment and a source of pride for rural women. Punjab's Phulkari has been a traditional emblem and a part of wedding paraphernalia since ancient times. The traditional bagh and phulkari are not confined to traditional wedding trunks but have transcended the geographical and cultural boundaries of Punjab, making an international appearance. With intricate embroidery and vibrant colours, Phulkari has made its mark on the international fashion setting. The fusion of traditional phulkari and contemporary trends with the amalgamation of technology has tapped the potential of this ancient craft. Phulkari was on the edge of extinction prior to the advent of social media, but after being endangered, it was not only restored but also gained popularity among many fashion designers and art enthusiasts (Gupta, 2015).

With the onset of technological advancements, the 'Art of Phulkari' has reached global platforms, making it a boon. Social commerce platforms are transforming the Phulkari world for a variety of reasons. The commercialization of Phulkari and the accessibility and viability of a variety of Phulkari products, such as kurtas, pouches, home décor pieces, juttis, cell covers, file folders, etc., are a few of the outcomes (Veenu et al., 2017). But on the flip side, technology is seen as a bane to this traditional art. Computerized embroidery, machine work, and duplicity at cheaper rates have flooded the global market today. Phulkari has travelled from a bridal trousseau to fashion runways, making it a part of fast fashion. Fast fashion poses

⁹ Products with a certain place of origin are protected by a Geographical Indication tag, a type of intellectual property protection.

a challenge to sustainable fashion. The rapid consumption and production of cheaply made goods contribute to environmental degradation. The loss of unique charm and authentic work is the second major concern. Third, more machines mean less requirement of labour, leading to unemployment. This sets a cycle of waste and a cycle of unemployment which hampers the economy of a nation.

During the revolution, automation brought Phulkari into the contemporary era. Its timeless beauty and inventiveness have helped it regain popularity in the market in recent years. (Randhawa, 2019). Due to growing appreciation and awareness of traditional crafts and sustainability, the market for these goods has expanded. The intricate details and imperfections in the handcrafted phulkari actually make it a one-of-a-kind product. It is important to strike a balance between this intricate handcrafted art and emerging technology to protect the historical and cultural significance attached to it.

New initiatives have been launched by the State and Central Governments, NGOs, designers, and business people in an attempt to bring back the lost craft of phulkari as a cottage industry (Kaur, 2011). MBCT is working tirelessly to receive and sustain the traditional art of Phulkari through their team of 'MBCT Phulkari Makers'¹⁰. They are providing free of cost training, actively engaging rural women, and generating resources to empower them and preserve their skills. The promotion of sustainable production and consumption of phulkari products is their main concern.

Rural women who are still deprived of the liberty to walk out from household responsibilities can enhance their livelihood by utilizing technology in online platforms to outsource their intricate handmade creations and become self-sufficient entrepreneurs. The gap between rural and urban can be bridged by harnessing the potential of technology. The whisper of a rural house in Punjab has the potential to be a loud triumph on the global platform.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

According to Veenu (2017), social commerce leverages social media to facilitate the purchase and sale of various goods and services while also fostering customer relationships. This study examined the effects of online marketplaces on the global selling of Phulkari, which has led to a regular income stream and an improvement in the socioeconomic standing of Phulkari artisans. According to Kapila (2020) Phulkari has made a significant impact on the fashion industry, undergone numerous reinventions, and gained recognition both domestically and internationally. Punjab, Haryana, and Rajasthan have been granted the Geographical Indication (GI) designation for phulkari in order to safeguard this artistic creation. The purpose of this study was to determine the degree of awareness regarding this traditional needlework among different stakeholders, and it was conducted in the districts of Patiala and Amritsar. Only thirty percent of the respondents were found to be engaged in this craft for financial gain. Many artists were unable to distinguish between embroidery produced

¹⁰ MBCT Phulkari Makers (PMBP) is a financially independent self-help-group which evolved organically out of the vocational training initiatives at Mehar Baba Charitable Trust in the year 2009.

by computerized machinery and embroidery produced by hand. A great deal of folk art has emerged throughout history as a result of Phulkari's transformation to modern technology. Its timeless beauty and creativity have helped it reclaim market share in recent years. By empowering rural women in Punjab, this commercial phulkari has currently improved living conditions for a large number of them and boosted the rural economy. The study illustrates how to use leisure time as a means of subsistence in the modern world (Randhawa, 2019). Globalization and colonization have caused a decline in needlework, but the passion for the skill has made it possible to revive it with cutting-edge modern techniques. With the use of digital applications, such as CAD/CAM and Photopaint, traditional themes can be updated. The newest automatic machinery helps to produce more at a rapid pace by replacing the labour-intensive and time-consuming traditional ways. In order for traditional Phulkari needlework to endure in the contemporary fashion market, this would assist blend it with modernity (Kaur, 2018). Social media is a communication tool that disseminates knowledge and information using a variety of sources. In this environment, Punjabi folk art, or Phulkari, has evolved through a variety of media, such as websites, blogs, e-papers, social networking sites like Facebook and Twitter, and so forth. This corpus of work has made a significant contribution to raising awareness of Phulkari and transforming the needlework from its artisanal status to a more commercial one. As a result, social media and digitization have contributed to the empowerment of Punjabi women (Gupta,

2015). The decline of this traditional handicraft has been attributed to a lack of experience, middlemen taking advantage of the craftspeople, and a physical and communication barrier to accessing the craftsmen. India is caught between the past and the future, tradition and technology, and local haats giving way to commercial malls in the new millennium. Craft, however, continues to hold its position and continues to discover new prospects around the globe (Kaur, 2011). Ila Gupta (2014) focuses on the traditional Phulkari folk art of Punjab and how organizations like the Punjab Small Industries and Export Corporation (PSIEC) and the Patiala Handicraft Workshop Cooperative Industrial Society Ltd. are bringing it back to life in the province's major cities. Phulkari has a significant impact on socio-cultural relationships as well, as it is typically given as a dowry. Due to the advent of commercial Phulkari, traditional art is currently suffering greatly. But in the present era, the commercial Phulkari has given many rural women a means of subsistence and, by empowering rural women in Punjab, has made a significant economic contribution to the rural area.

The goal of this study was to find out how training affected rural women's acquisition of knowledge. Twenty women from the villages of Ladwa and Dabra in the state of Haryana's Hisar district were chosen. They received training for fifteen days. The material utilized and tips for phulkari embroidery were determined to have been sufficiently learned by the respondents. The calculated value was judged to be significant at the 1 and 5% levels of significance. It was determined that rural women's knowledge of phulkari

embroidery has increased as a result of training exposure (Saini, 2014). The majority of the women's work is in embroidery, whereas the men trade. Women who achieve financial independence are enabled to take on more of an autonomous role in their families, communities, and the political, social, educational, and gender domains. Therefore, the goal of this study was to investigate how the adoption of Phulkari craft has impacted the social and economic empowerment of female Phulkari craftsmen in the Patiala District's Tripuri district (Kohli, 2020).

Navigating the interplay between Fast Fashion and Slow Fashion

Phulkari, being a traditional craft, inherently embodies sustainability. It involves hand embroidery techniques passed down through generations, using locally sourced materials and natural dyes. The slow and meticulous process of creating Phulkari pieces promotes the idea of slow fashion, where quality and longevity are valued over mass production and quick trends. On the other hand, fast fashion, which emphasizes cheap and trendy clothing produced rapidly, can sometimes overlook the traditional craftsmanship and cultural significance of Phulkari. This can lead to cultural appropriation or exploitation of the craft and its artisans. However, there is a growing awareness and movement towards incorporating sustainable practices in the fashion industry. Many designers and brands are now collaborating with Phulkari artisans, promoting ethical sourcing, fair trade practices, and environmentally friendly production methods. This helps in preserving the authenticity of Phulkari

while supporting the livelihoods of the artisans. By recognizing the cultural significance of Phulkari and supporting sustainable practices, we can contribute to achieving these SDGs and create a positive impact on both the artisans and society.

The 4Ps of Phulkari Production in rural areas-

4 Ps (product, promotion, price, place) in relation to Phulkari production in rural areas.

- i. **Product:** Phulkari is a traditional embroidery art form that originates from Punjab, India. The product is intricately handcrafted with vibrant threads. The product maintains its authenticity, quality, and cultural significance while adapting to modern trends.
- ii. **Promotion:** Promoting Phulkari production in rural areas is done through various channels. Social media platforms, local exhibitions, and collaborations with fashion designers can create awareness and reach a wider audience. Showcasing the craftsmanship, uniqueness, and cultural heritage of Phulkari can attract customers and generate interest.
- iii. **Price:** Determining the price of Phulkari products requires careful consideration. Factors such as the cost of raw materials, labour, and market demand should be taken into account. Balancing affordability for customers while ensuring fair wages for artisans is crucial to sustain the Phulkari industry in rural areas.
- iv. **Place:** It's important to establish production centres in areas where

the craft has historical roots and where skilled artisans are readily available. This helps preserve the traditional techniques and empowers local communities by providing employment opportunities.

Figure 1 Parameters For Evaluation of the Study

Source: Authors' Compilation

Overall, focusing on the 4Ps in Phulkari production in rural areas can help create a sustainable and thriving industry with the judicious use of technology and modern techniques of production and promotion.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Tech Triumph: Onset Of Digital Technology

In today's fast paced world, technology plays a crucial role in almost every aspect of our lives. It has transformed our way of living. The key benefit of digital technology is its ability to connect people from all around the globe. The world is a smaller place today due to the development of ITC. The endless opportunities for collaboration and knowledge sharing across the globe are possible with just one click. Digital technology has revolutionized industries and businesses. As of 2021, about 4.7 billion individuals are actively utilizing the

internet, according to Intellipat. The number of people using social media worldwide is already above 3.5 billion, and by 2025, it is predicted to reach 4.41 billion. Approximately 60% of all marketing is digital in nature. With the internet at our fingertips, digital technology provides us with instant access to lifelong learning, and personalized education at any time and from anywhere in the world.

The Journey Of "Phulkari"

Phulkari refers to Punjabi traditional needlework. The word consists of two words- Phul (flowers) and Akari (shapes). It has been a significant part of our colours from the timeless tale 'Heer Ranjha' and as soon as we hear the word 'Phulkari' a beautiful picture of Punjab comes to our mind. This is how embedded it is in the roots of Punjab. The traditional Phulkari represents the hard, colourful, and demanding life that Punjabi women lead.

"Main kadna Dilli darwaza, Pachian di lia de logri. (I will embroider the Delhi gate, Oh, get me twenty-five rupees worth of yarn.)

Khoonh vich pani, man meri rani Kadegi kasidhra, paegi madhani!"(Water in the well, my mother is a queen, She is busy embroidering the "churn" motif.)"

The history of phulkari art dates back to the fifteenth century AD. The earliest known items are Phulkari shawls and handkerchiefs, which were stitched in the Chamba style in the fifteenth century by Bebe Nanaki, the sister of the first Sikh teacher, teacher Nanak Dev ji (1469-1539). These artefacts are kept in Punjab's Sikh holy sites. The history of the art form is said to have been traced as far back as

Greek rule. The delight inherent in this rural art form was amplified through the process of stitching folk tunes onto the fabric. A single phulkari is the result of several people working together, not just one person. One certain present given during marriages was phulkari. Because of this, the traditional phulkari's patterns and hues have deep symbolic meaning. It portrays Punjab's rural heritage and culture.

Phulkari 2.0: Harnessing The Power of Technology for Revitalization

Phulkari 2.0 represents a dynamic approach to preserving and promoting this cherished craft, leveraging the power of technology to propel it into the future. Expert art historian Dr Alka Pande has been a vocal supporter of Phulkari and Bagh preservation. She is in charge of naming some of the most prominent and up-and-coming sculptors, photographers, and artists as well as organizing a number of noteworthy and insightful shows in India and outside. Outside of Punjab, phulkari is relatively unknown unlike chikankari and Gujarati mirror artwork. Both of these needlework styles have benefited greatly from the efforts of organizations such as Dastaar and SEWA (The Lifestyle Journalist, 2024). There has been a renewed interest in learning and preserving the techniques of Phulkari embroidery. The pandemic of 2020 exposed a number of Indian artists who saw stitch arts as descriptive pieces of art rather than just light-hearted amusement. To bring them into line with contemporary usage and the global marketplace, reconfiguration is essential. Supervisors who understand the rich history of India's needlework are essential for managing the country's expanding semi-

skilled labour force. Innovation and tradition can and should work together (Punam Madhok, 2023). By bridging the digital divide, Phulkari artisans are empowered to embrace technology and leverage its potential for their craft's advancement. Customers can purchase phulkari embroidery-related things by using various online shopping sites or these Facebook social media platforms, where sellers publish photographs of their wares. (Chitrolekha International Magazine on Art and Design, 5(2), 2015)

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study is based on the development of a sustainable future for fashion and analyzing the 4Ps - Product, Price, Place, and Promotion in the rural setting of district Fatehgarh Sahib. This paper attempts to explore the preservation of traditional craft while integrating modern techniques to empower women. The scope of India's stitch arts is expanding because of innovative interpretations used by modern artists. The 2020 pandemic uncovered a number of Indian artists who viewed stitch arts as descriptive works of art rather than merely recreational tools (Kejriwal, 2022). Phulkari found a way to thrive by embracing technology in challenging COVID-19 times by connecting customers across the globe. Phulkari has not only been able to adapt and flourish in the world of contemporary fashion trends but also has played a crucial role in the economic empowerment of women making them self-sufficient. Since Fatehgarh Sahib is the birthplace of sewing machines, it has been an initiator of the incorporation of technology in textiles. With the amalgamation of technology through 'Digital Marketing Skill Trainings',

this paper addresses the need for innovative solutions with a focus on the symbolic and socio-cultural significance of Phulkari. By leveraging digital platforms, the revival of the intricate artistry of Phulkari is possible which will contribute to the enhancement of the livelihoods of rural women. This paper identifies the possibilities of combining tradition with technology.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The present paper attempts to improve the living conditions of rural women with the help of technology and innovation in District Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab. The research objectives include:

i. Evaluating the socio-economic

impact of incorporating design and digital technology on the livelihoods of rural Punjabi women.

ii. Exploring the **potential of integrating design and digital technology** in the Phulkari craft to enhance its marketability and reach.

iii. Developing **training programs and capacity-building initiatives** to empower rural Punjabi women in utilizing design and digital technology for the Phulkari craft.

iv. **Assessing the sustainability and long-term viability** of incorporating design and digital technology in the Phulkari craft.

LOCALE OF THE STUDY

Figure 2 Map of Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab

Source: Map of District, Fatehgarh Sahib, Government of Punjab. <https://fatehgarhsahib.nic.in/map-of-district/>

Located in the northwest Indian state of Punjab, Fatehgarh Sahib is a city and significant Sikh pilgrimage site. Agriculture, industry, and associated sectors are the main drivers of the district's economy. A significant place in history has been gained by Fatehgarh

Sahib. In the district of Fatehgarh Sahib, the study covered 100+ village clusters of Digital (1019) and Phulkari training (582) and had an influence on 1022 rural women and 63 men who were craftsmen, small business owners, etc.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND SAMPLING

The participatory research approach was incorporated to involve women artisans in this research project. To gather data, a combination of quantitative and qualitative research analysis was found to be ideal. Qualitative Analysis included one-to-one interaction, discussions, observations, research studies, field visits, case studies, record keeping, decoding data, ethnographic research, documentation, and interpretations. Quantitative Analysis includes Questionnaires, data collection and data processing. The focus is to know the “What and Why” of the social phenomenon. Likert scale was used to analyse the responses. Transparency and ethical concerns were kept in mind while dealing with the people of rural areas to ensure that the values of social work were upheld. The consent from the participants was taken to maintain confidentiality. All the potential risks or imbalances were recognized beforehand to mitigate them to reduce wastage of resources. This approach helped to gather in-depth information and capture a diverse range of perspectives.

Figure 3 Phulkari Making Significance Measure

In rural Punjab, Phulkari is not just a form of art but also a symbol of heritage and identity. These embroidered pieces are often passed down through generations, carrying stories and memories within the intricate patterns. Rural Punjabi women face various challenges, including limited market access and lack of design innovation. 93.12 % believe that the art of phulkari making is lost because of the use of technology and machines.

This study examined sustainable digital development and incorporation of technology in rural areas of district Fatehgarh Sahib. The training included both Digital and Phulkari training. The sample size of this paper was taken as 1085 (1019 Digital Trainees, 582 Phulkari) respondents and the training of trainers (TOTs) strategy was built from a pool of competent instructors. The respondents included 94% females and 6% males. The trainers were also evaluated in this study.

Figure 4 Gender Profile of Respondents

Gender Profile of the Respondents

1. Socio-Economic Impact

Phulkari craft has immense cultural and economic significance in Fatehgarh Sahib. Even though phulkari is a traditional and original art of Punjab 69.28% respondents

were ‘freshers’ in phulkari making. The findings below in the pie chart shows that there is 88.3% cultural significance which is the highest among social, economic and cultural.

Figure 5 Significance of Phulkari

- **Livelihood enhancement:** 99.14% of the respondents assert that phulkari training provided them with enough livelihood enhancement opportunities.

Figure 6 Intent behind Learning the Art of Phulkari

- **Growth in local businesses and entrepreneurship:** 56.70% of respondents joined the training to revive and commercialize the phulkari. The provision of necessary skills and knowledge will help rural people build a sustainable livelihood.

- **Enhancements in gender equality and women’s empowerment:** By providing women with the opportunity to learn and master this traditional art form, Phulkari

training programs have not only preserved cultural heritage but also empowered women economically and socially. Phulkari training programs have boosted women’s self-esteem and confidence, empowering them to take on leadership roles and challenge gender norms. 74% believed that their phulkari skills have significantly improved post-training.

Figure 7 Improvement in Phulkari Embroidery Skills Post Training

2. Technology Intervention

Design and digital technology interventions can enhance the production efficiency and market reach of Phulkari craft. 78.35% respondents were keen to pass on the knowledge of Phulkari to future generations. The integration of design and digital technology in the phulkari craft industry opens up a world of possibilities.

Figure 8 Future of Phulkari Skills

- **Proficiency levels in utilizing technology:** 82.7% of trainees considered themselves as more confident after undergoing an eight-days training programme with MBCT based on tech-savvy techniques.

- **Access to digital infrastructure and connectivity:** 7.65% of respondents had no access to the internet. Initiatives like providing internet connectivity and promoting digital literacy empower rural residents to connect to the global world and be a part of the digital economy.

- **Collaboration with fashion and textile designers:** exploring new design possibilities and creation of contemporary and innovative products using Phulkari. The collaboration enabled local artisans to be a part of the global market. There are various designers with whom collaboration has been done including Nikita Shah (USA) - "Do Bhavre"; Arshia Singh - "Noor" and In-House Collaboration MBCT "Hunar"- Dr. Kavita Marriya (Former Principal, Home Science College, Chandigarh), Shruti Nigam Hema, Ashna, and Satwinder.

Figure 9 Changes Post Training

3. Community Engagement and Capacity Building

- **Number of community members actively involved in project activities:** The participatory approach enables stakeholders to be a part of the project from the beginning. Stakeholders included District Administration, Fatehgarh Sahib, Government Home Science College, Chandigarh; MBCT team; CFLI team; Department of Public Administration, Panjab University; News and Media; CCS HAU Hisar; Designers; NIFT Panchkula and NIIFT Mohali; GGSDS College, Chandigarh; Fraser Valley India, Chandigarh and community representatives.

- **Community engagement and participation in decision-making processes:** Outreaching and identifying the people with creative minds and their eagerness to know more about landed them in the Master Trainers' Program. 49 artisans were registered with the Ministry of Textiles, Government of India and provided artisan identity cards.

- **Level of community engagement and sustainability of project initiatives:** At the end of the training in every village, women presented a map of Fatehgarh Sahib made by them consisting of intricate Phulkari motifs to their respective Sarpanches. On the last day of the training, most of the women got their suits and dupattas traced with the help of the MBCT Team so that they could improve their hand embroidery skills. The request to conduct more stitching and embroidery workshops in the villages was made by local people.

4. Environmental Sustainability and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Training programs and skill development initiatives are crucial for empowering rural Punjabi women in the craft sector. As shown in Figure 6 56.70% respondents

joined the training to revive and commercialize the phulkari. Provision of necessary skills and knowledge will help rural people build a sustainable livelihood.

Figure 10 Sustainability and Securing Future of Phulkari Skills

- **Awareness about fast fashion and sustainable fashion:** 77% of trainees agreed that sustainable fashion is far better than fast fashion and knowledge of phulkari should be transferred to the future generations to reach sustainability.

- **collection related to upcycling of products:** Rural women are conscious

about the environment and support sustainability in the form of second-hand clothing, supporting local artisans, upcycling old fabrics etc. Not only this, conscious consumption reduces environmental risks such as excessive waste, exploitation of workers, and depletion of resources.

- **Alignment of project goals with specific SDGs:** The project aligns with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and reflects the intention to bring a change from the bottom levels of society.

- **Progress made towards achieving SDG targets related to rural development, technology, and sustainability:** Small steps like upcycling fabrics, using second hand clothing, and conscious consumption pattern aligns with SDG goals. Various workshops and seminars have been conducted by the designers in order to orient the trainees with the latest designs and techniques.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS:

Figure 11 Infographic of Results and Findings

Source: Authors' Compilation from Canva design App

Phulkari in Digital Spotlight: A Pathway to Women Empowerment

While Phulkari embroidery is a traditional art form deeply rooted in the cultural heritage of Punjab, digital marketing is a modern concept that utilizes technology and online platforms to promote products and services. In recent years, there has been a growing trend of promoting and selling Phulkari products through digital platforms. This has opened up new opportunities for artisans in rural areas to showcase their work to a wider audience and connect with potential customers beyond their local communities. Through social media platforms, websites, and online marketplaces, artisans can share images and stories behind their Phulkari creations, attracting customers from different parts of India and even globally. This digital exposure helps create awareness and demand for Phulkari products, thereby supporting the livelihoods of artisans and contributing to the preservation of this traditional craft. Digital marketing also enables artisans to collaborate with designers, retailers, and organizations that specialize in promoting traditional crafts. These partnerships can help expand the reach of Phulkari embroidery and create sustainable market opportunities for artisans in rural India. Overall, the linkage between Phulkari and digital marketing in rural India is an exciting development that allows artisans to leverage technology to promote and sell their beautiful creations. It brings women to the spotlight and enables them to lead from the front. This is a wonderful example of how traditional art forms can thrive in the digital age while preserving their cultural significance.

Phulkari aligns with several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) set by the United Nations. The phulkari training program in rural villages of Punjab is not just about the preservation of the art form, but also about the contribution to rural renaissance. The revival of culture through Phulkari training in rural villages of Punjab is a unique way to preserve and promote traditional art which is also creating a renewed sense of cultural pride and economic opportunities for the artisans. By incorporating the 4 Ps of marketing - production, promotion, price, and place - sustainable opportunities are created for the artisans. Additionally, embracing digitalization will have a positive impact, helping to reach a wider audience and ensuring the longevity of this art form.

OVERCOMING THE ROADBLOCKS

- i. **Difficulty in Data Collection: The Issue of Illiteracy-** which made it difficult to use Google Forms for filling out the questionnaire. Some participants were unable to read or write and it became challenging to gather data using an online platform like Google Forms. A workshop for TOTs was conducted to teach them the use of Google Forms and on field presence of a tech-savvy MBCT member was ensured.
- ii. **More Inclination towards Phulkari Training than Digital training:** A stronger inclination towards Phulkari training rather than Digital training was seen during the project because people were eager to learn this traditional folk art of embroidery,

- secondly people were not aware of the significance of online product presence. Thus, an initiative was taken to raise awareness about the digital presence of the products which aligned with the objects of the project.
- iii. Lack of Infrastructure: Limited access to infrastructure and internet was acknowledged and community centres were recognised for training. The digital devices were recharged with sufficient internet packs to ensure smooth transmission during training.
 - iv. Miscellaneous recommendations based on the problems faced are as follows:
 - (i) Organize design and digital technology workshops to provide training and support to Phulkari artisans.
 - (ii) Create platforms for collaboration between designers, artisans, and market experts to thrive in the digital age.
 - (iii) Develop an e-commerce platform to promote and sell Phulkari products globally.
 - (iv) Strengthen marketing and branding efforts to increase the demand for Phulkari craft by empowering rural women in the revival of the 'phulan di kalakari'.
 - (v) It is a transformative endeavor that aims to empower rural Punjabi women through the integration of design and digital technology.
- smartphones, computers, and the Internet is limited. This impacted the extent to which women artisans could fully engage with and benefit from the technological aspects of the project.
2. Language and literacy barriers: Limited proficiency in digital platforms or English, posed challenges in effectively utilizing technology for promotion and online marketing.
 3. Infrastructure and connectivity issues: Rural areas often face infrastructure challenges, including inconsistent electricity supply and poor internet connectivity. These factors hindered the seamless integration of technology into Phulkari production and promotion.
 4. Resistance to change: Introducing technology into traditional practices faced resistance from some artisans who are accustomed to traditional methods. Overcoming this resistance and ensuring acceptance and adoption of technology required additional effort and time.
 5. Financial constraints: Technology can be costly to implement and maintain. Limited financial resources among the women artisans may pose a challenge in terms of investing in the necessary equipment and training required for the project.
 6. Cultural preservation concerns: As technology influences Phulkari production, there are concerns about preserving the authenticity and cultural heritage of this art form. Striking a balance between innovation and cultural preservation will be important.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. Limited access to technology: In rural areas, access to technology such as

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, despite the fact that traditional Phulkari is vanishing, numerous

NGOs are attempting to bring it back to life. The quality and longevity of Punjab's traditional Phulkari have been weakened by the commercialization of modern Phulkari. These days, neither personal use nor gifting is involved. These days, Punjabi women gain from it since it is done for profit. The delight inherent in this rural art form was amplified through the process of stitching folk tunes onto the fabric. A single phulkari is the result of several people working together, not just one person. Making Phulkari now isn't as labour-intensive and meticulous as it was in the past in rural, traditional settings. Still, the classic Phulkari has a more appealing appearance than the modern version. The government has been trying to promote Punjabi Phulkari by holding competitions, fairs, exhibitions, and special training programs. One benefit of this renaissance is that it is giving many impoverished people—especially women—jobs. These days, Phulkari is well-known outside of Punjab as well as abroad. The author(s) received financial support for the research by CFLI.

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